

Investigating Floodplain Forest Phenology Using Dense Satellite Time Series along the Drava River, Croatia

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Abstract: Floodplain forests are valuable but increasingly endangered landscapes, threatened by human pressures that drive habitat decline and environmental change. The Drava River in Croatia is among the most preserved lowland rivers in the Pannonian Basin with a wide vegetated corridor, yet it is impacted by dam construction that has significantly altered its hydrology and geomorphology. Here, we used Harmonized Landsat-Sentinel (HLS) data to investigate floodplain forest phenology from 2016 to 2024 in two study areas: one located between two accumulation reservoirs and dams, and the other farther downstream in a reach with less pronounced human impacts. Key phenological metrics, start of season (SOS) and end of season (EOS), were derived from EVI2 time series using the R package phenofit. To investigate drivers of spatio-temporal patterns, we analysed climatic variables (temperature, precipitation) and hydrological variables (discharge, groundwater levels). The results showed that SOS varied more strongly between years than between sites and it was significantly negatively associated with mean March temperature. In contrast, EOS occurred, on average, more than 30 days earlier at the upstream dam-impacted site, where river incision and reduced discharge presumably contributed to lower groundwater levels. These findings suggest that, in addition to climate, hydrological conditions strongly influence floodplain forest phenology, highlighting the role of human impacts in shaping riparian ecosystem processes in regulated riverine environments.

Keywords: vegetation dynamics; floodplain; groundwater; climatic drivers; HLS.

1 Introduction

Vegetation phenology describes the seasonal cycles of green-up and senescence. Although these cycles may appear stable, their timing varies annually depending on environmental conditions, primarily temperature and precipitation. As climate change increasingly affects ecosystem dynamics, growing attention has been directed toward understanding its influence on vegetation phenology as an indicator of broader environmental change (de Beurs and Henebry 2013, Piao et al. 2019).

Floodplain vegetation is particularly vulnerable to these changes due to intensive human activity within river corridors. River regulation, dam construction, and channelization alter natural flow regimes and reduce lateral connectivity between the river channel and floodplain (Mason et al. 2025). These modifications affect floodplain forests through increased water stress caused by reduced groundwater availability, leading to shifts in

structure, species distribution and phenology (Li et al. 2022, Petit et al. 2018). However, the patterns and drivers of floodplain forest phenology remain insufficiently understood, particularly in dam-regulated rivers where natural processes have been significantly altered.

Remote sensing provides an important tool for investigating river and vegetation dynamics, especially through dense satellite time series that enable monitoring of large areas at high temporal resolution (Betz et al. 2023). Such datasets are particularly valuable for vegetation phenology studies, as the extraction of phenological metrics requires continuous temporal observations (Kong et al. 2022).

This study aims to (i) extract key phenological metrics (start and end of the growing season) of floodplain forests along the Drava River using dense satellite time series and (ii) analyse the spatial and temporal variability of phenological metrics in two study areas, one located upstream and the other downstream from dams and hydropower plants.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The Drava River is one of the largest lowland rivers in the Pannonian Basin, characterized by a relatively well-preserved meandering pattern and a wide riparian corridor despite substantial human impacts. In the Croatian section of the river, major engineering works have included river straightening and meander cutoffs since the nineteenth century. These interventions have resulted in channel narrowing, reduced sinuosity, and expansion of floodplain vegetation (Kiss and Andradi 2017). Furthermore, in the 1980s three hydropower plants were constructed in the upper Croatian course of the river near Varaždin. Flow regulation associated with dam construction substantially reduced flood discharges and sediment transport, leading to channel incision and further channel narrowing (Oskoruš and Bonacci 2010).

In this study, we examined floodplain forest phenology in the upper Croatian section of the river in two sites: one located between two accumulation reservoirs and dams (A in Figure 1), in a river reach characterized by a significantly reduced discharge, and another farther downstream in a reach with less pronounced human impacts (B in Figure 1). Both sites were characterized by stable forest vegetation. Absolute elevation of the site A is 153 m a.s.l., and that of site B is 124 m a.s.l.

Figure 1. Drava River section showing floodplain forest study sites (A – upstream dam-impacted site, B – downstream site).

2.2 Earth Observation data processing

Earth observation satellite data were obtained from the Harmonized Landsat–Sentinel (HLS) dataset, which provides 30 m spatial resolution and a 2–3-day revisit time (Claverie et al. 2018). The image collection was pre-processed, including cloud masking using the Fmask-based quality assessment layer provided within the NASA HLS product. Enhanced Vegetation Index 2 (EVI2, Jiang et al. 2008) values were extracted from the masked HLS dataset using equation (1) using a 30 m buffer within each site for the period 2016–2024. EVI2 was used instead of NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) because it showed better results in further extraction of phenological metrics (e.g. Feng et al. 2025).

$$EVI2 = 2.5 \times \frac{NIR-Red}{NIR+2.4 \times Red+1} \quad (1)$$

2.3 Extraction of phenological metrics

Phenological metrics were calculated in R using the phenofit package (Kong et al. 2022). EVI2 time series were processed using the Whittaker–Harmonic Analysis of Time Series (wHANTS) fitting function for season detection, which is recommended for natural vegetation with clear and stable seasonal dynamics (Kong et al. 2022). Subsequently, the Beck method was applied for fine-scale curve fitting and phenological metric extraction, as it produced the lowest error rates and the fewest missing values. For each site and year, we derived the day of year (DOY) corresponding to the start (SOS) and end (EOS) of the growing season.

2.4 Relationship between phenology and environmental variables

Investigated environmental drivers of vegetation phenology included climatic and hydrological variables. Climate data (temperature, precipitation) were obtained from the gridded E-OBS dataset (Cornes et al. 2018) and extracted for each site using the *terra* package in R (Hijmans et al. 2024). Hydrological data, including groundwater levels and river discharge, were obtained from the Croatian Meteorological and Hydrological Service. Groundwater data were interpolated using

RBFInterpolator (radial basis function) implemented in Python (`scipy.interpolate.RBFInterpolator`), based on 60 monitoring stations in the wider floodplain, and subsequently extracted for each site. Because discharge data were available from only two hydrological stations in the study area, a single representative value was assigned to each site. For both climate and hydrological variables, monthly means and 2-month lagged values were calculated.

Relationships between phenological metrics (SOS, EOS) and environmental variables were statistically tested using Spearman’s correlation. Temporal dynamics of phenological metrics were explored by analyzing time series trends (Mann-Kendall test) and boxplots for visualization. Spatial dynamics were assessed by comparing phenological metrics between the upstream and downstream site using boxplots and statistical tests (Mann-Whitney U-test).

3 Results

3.1 Spatio-temporal variability of the phenological metrics

Analyses of spatio-temporal variability of phenological metrics in the two investigated sites revealed notable differences. Regarding SOS, the downstream site exhibited significant interannual variability, however, its mean value (DOY = 97) was not statistically significantly different from that of the upstream reach (DOY = 99). The earliest recorded onset of SOS occurred in 2024 (DOY = 83), while the latest was observed in 2018 (DOY = 110), both at the downstream site (Figure 2). No statistically significant trend was detected in the SOS time series over the study period.

In contrast, EOS showed clear spatial variation, with differences in values between the two studied sites. The downstream reach exhibited a statistically significantly later EOS (DOY = 298) compared to the upstream reach (DOY = 267) on average, as confirmed by the Mann–Whitney U test ($p < 0.001$). Similarly to SOS, no statistically significant temporal trend was observed in the EOS time series.

Figure 2. Interannual variability of SOS and EOS in the two study sites.

3.2 Environmental drivers of floodplain forest phenology

Spearman’s correlation analysis indicated that only mean March temperature showed a statistically significant relationship with the phenological metric SOS, with correlation coefficients of $\rho = -0.904$ ($p = 0.002$) at the upstream site and $\rho = -0.845$ ($p = 0.004$) at the downstream site. These results suggest that higher March temperatures are associated with earlier SOS (Figure 3). None of the other tested predictor variables exhibited statistically significant relationships with the phenological metrics (SOS or EOS).

However, it should be noted that although no statistically significant Spearman correlation was found for EOS, a comparison of mean values suggests a clear distinction between sites. Specifically, in the upstream dam-impacted reach, the mean groundwater depth (2.39 m) was greater compared to the downstream reach (1.48 m), indicating a potentially meaningful hydrological difference that is not captured by the correlation analysis (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Relationship between mean temperature in March and SOS at the downstream site ($y = 122.74 - 3.49x$, $R^2 = 0.503$, $\rho = 0.032$).

Figure 4. Boxplots showing EOS (DOY) and mean groundwater depth (m) in the two study sites.

4 Discussion

The only statistically significant relationship between phenological metrics and environmental variables was found for SOS and mean March temperature, which exhibited a strong negative correlation at both sites. This finding suggests that warmer early spring conditions consistently lead to earlier onset of the growing season, in line with well-established temperature sensitivity of vegetation phenology in temperate climates (Lochin et al. 2024), as well as of riparian environments in drier climates (Sharif and Attarchi 2024).

In contrast, EOS exhibited a clearer and more persistent site-dependent pattern. The downstream site consistently showed later EOS compared to the upstream dam-impacted site, indicating a longer growing season downstream. The upstream site is located at a higher absolute elevation (30 m difference). However, more relevant might be its higher relative floodplain elevation with respect to mean water level in the channel, which is 2.7 m compared to 1.8 m at the downstream site.

Correspondingly, groundwater depth is also greater at the upstream site. Although no statistically significant Spearman correlations were detected (likely due to the limited sample size), greater groundwater depth in the upstream reach may have contributed to reduced water availability and earlier senescence (Pettit et al. 2018). This pattern may reflect the influence of human alterations to the river system in the upstream reach, including dam construction, reservoir formation, and artificial canal networks, which have reduced discharge in the main channel and likely contributed to groundwater decline and river incision. These findings should be further validated using a larger sample size covering different sections of the river floodplain with contrasting environmental conditions.

5 Conclusions

This study successfully extracted phenological metrics for two sites in the Drava River floodplain using dense satellite time series (HLS) in the period 2016–2024. The results revealed spatial differences in floodplain forest phenology, with the downstream site experiencing later EOS by more than 30 days on average. Overall, the findings suggest contrasting controls on phenological phases: SOS appears predominantly climate-driven, whereas EOS is presumably more strongly regulated by site-specific hydrological conditions potentially modified by dam influence. This highlights the importance of considering both climatic and hydrological factors when assessing vegetation phenology in regulated river systems.

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